

NONLINEAR STATIC AND DYNAMIC ANALYSIS OF DUCTILE ENGINEERED CEMENTITIOUS COMPOSITE

A Thesis

of

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ABSTRACT

The experimental probation is only to ascertain mechanical properties of polypropylene reinforced composite. The numerical investigations carried out on polyvinyl alcohol reinforced composite member and structural model subjected to moment-curvature relations, static incremental loads and earthquake motions are presented in this paper. A six storeys building models of both conventional concrete and fiber reinforced composite are analyzed to investigate the development of moment-curvature relations, incremental loads and dynamic behavior of the structures using software (ETABS 15).

Nonlinear customized hinge is used in nonlinear static analysis and a modified EI Centro earthquake motion is used in software (ETABS 15) as ground motion for nonlinear dynamic analysis. EI Centro earthquake motion was modified from the original EI Centro earthquake (1940) ground data.

The experiments of polypropylene reinforced composite demonstrate that the stain and deformation capacities are significantly higher than conventional concrete. The software (ETABS 15) result shows that the poly vinyl alcohol reinforced composite models have greater capacity of load, moment and ductility than the conventional structural models. Poly vinyl alcohol reinforced composite models show significant seismic survival performance and capacity than the models of conventional concrete.

Comparison of numerical results between poly vinyl alcohol reinforced composite models and conventional concrete models using software (ETABS 15) show a great profile of ductility, survival capacity, economy and environment friendliness.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Basic Concept:

Concrete is a composite material obtained by mixing cementing materials, water and aggregate (and sometimes admixtures). It is not a homogeneous material like steel which is strong in both tension and compression. Interfacial Transition Zone is the weakest link in the concrete micro-structure. When compressed, the interface only transfers compressive stresses from one aggregate to the next. Under tension, the aggregates try to pull away from each other so this zone has to bear tensile stresses to hold the whole system together. Since its strength is significantly weaker than the aggregates, so the failure starts at much lower stresses.

Ductility is a measure of tensile deformation (strain) capacity typically associated with ductile steel, for example, but not with concrete. As concrete is brittle, it has low tensile strength and low strain capacity. In fact, many deterioration and failures in the concrete structures are due to the brittle nature of the material. However, ductility of concrete can be established by reducing micro-pores and thereby increasing tensile strength. The disadvantages may be avoided by adding micro-fibers to the plain concrete. Incorporating micro-fibers provides a practical means of enhancing the ductility of concrete materials which is commonly known as engineered cementitious composite (ECC). Traditional concrete's lack of durability and failure under strain, both stemming from brittle behavior, has been a pushing factor in the development of ECC.

1.2 Context:

The addition of fibers to a brittle concrete matrix can improve substantially its tensile strength and reduce the tendency of cracking, which leads to enhanced ductility and toughness. Further, adding fibers to plain concrete can enhance greatly its tension-softening behavior under tensile load. The fibers cross the paths of potential cracks and transmit stress between the fibers and the matrix through the interfacial bond.

Ductility of concrete allows high deformation under sustained or time variant load. So taking advantage of ductile concrete the amount of reinforcement of RC structure can be reduced significantly. It can also be used in structural retrofitting as it gives high tensile and compressive strength as well as ductility (large deformation).

The concept of ductile concrete is very new in Bangladesh. In fact there is still no research work on ductile concrete, especially to enhance the ultimate strain of concrete. In the perspective of Bangladesh, designing of ductile concrete for different structures can be more cost effective comparing its structural performance. So this work on ductile concrete may give a new dimension to the RC structure and retrofitting in Bangladesh.

1.3 Literature Review:

As mentioned, ductility can be attained for normal concrete by using fibers with high tensile strength. Though there is no published research work on ductile concrete in Bangladesh but there are many publications on ductile concrete around the world. Attempts to achieve tensile ductility in concrete material are exemplified by the early efforts in 1970's and later with continuous aligned fibers. Interest in creating a fiber reinforced concrete (FRC) material with tensile ductility has been gaining ground since the 1980's. The toughness of the material is increased within FRC, but no change in ductility is attained.

The modern day version of continuous fiber reinforcement is represented by textile reinforced concrete materials and several engineered fibers as well. The continuous fiber reinforcement is represented by textile reinforced concrete materials that may be prestressed (Reinhardt et al. 2003, Curbach & Jesse 1999). Developed in parallel, the use of discontinuous fibers at high dosage (4~20%) such as in cement laminates (Allen 1971) and in SIFCON (Slurry Infiltrated Fiber Concrete) (Lankard 1986, Naaman 1992) has resulted in concrete composite materials that attain higher tensile strength than normal concrete and which are not as brittle, but with much less ductility than their continuous fiber and textile reinforced counterparts.

Especially, Engineered Cementitious Composite (ECC) is a micromechanically designed strain-hardening cementitious composite which exhibits extreme tensile strain capacity (typically more than 2%) through bridging of micro-cracks by the fibers and multiple cracking (Li & Leung 1992, Leung 1996).

To predict the mechanical behavior of ECC, the fiber bridging curve and crack spacing should be precisely evaluated. Kanda et al. (2000) proposed a theoretical approach for predicting the tensile stress-strain relation, which is expressed in terms of steady state cracking stress, ultimate strain, and ultimate stress, of random short-fiber-reinforced cement composites showing pseudo-strain hardening.

These may be considered a class of materials separate from FRC in that different degree of tensile ductility is achieved, often accompanied by a strain hardening response distinct from the tension-softening response of FRC: Naaman & Reinhardt (2003) classified such material as high performance

Fiber Reinforced Cementitious Composites (HPFRCC). Research on pultruded (continuous processed and manufactured composite materials) fiber reinforced concrete was pioneered by Mobasher et al. (2010). Micro synthetic fibers have been used to improve the toughness of quasi-brittle cement-based materials (Li 1991).

An experimental and numerical study of deflection behavior of concrete beams reinforced with PVA micro-fibers by Hamoush et al. (2010) shows how the strain capacity of concrete can be increased using micro-fibers.

A numerical study on nonlinear behavior of RC structure and moment curvature relation development was performed (Anam & Shoma 2002, Ćurić et al. 2016)

Thesis study at University of Asia Pacific on nonlinear seismic analysis by ETABS and ABAQUS was simulated by Talukdar & Rahman (2014).

Pushover analysis of seismic performance evaluation was analyzed for RC and ECC structures (Krawinkler & Seneviratna 1998, Ghobarah 2001). Numerical study on prediction of ECC tensile stress-strain curve based on modified fiber bridging relations considering fiber distribution characteristics (Kanda et al. 2000). A numerical observation on nonlinear dynamic properties of RC frames using cyclic moment-curvature relation (Kwak et al. 2004)

Light-weight ECC material performance and impact performance were assessed by Zhuge et al. (2014). Numerical modeling of mechanical behavior of engineered cementitious composites under axial tension by Ting & Zhang (2016) demonstrated the finite element method to justify the behavior of ECC under tension.

A number of research groups are developing ECC science, including those at the University of Michigan, University of California, Delft University of Technology, University of Tokyo, Czech Technical University and Stanford University.

1.4 Objective:

The objective of this study is basically to investigate the mechanical properties of ductile concrete and its performance by experimental and numerical analysis. It also specifically focuses on

Experimental works

Using different amounts of PVA (0.4% and 0.8%) to make various types of ECC samples, including four (4" × 8") cylinders (for compression test), four (1" × 1") briquettes (for tensile tests) and four 4'-long beams of (2" × 6") sections (for bending tests). The samples would be used to determine the

- Tensile strength and ultimate tensile strain by direct axial tensile tests on briquettes
- Compressive strength and ultimate compressive strain by cylinder tests
- Flexural strength and Deformation limit and of ductile concrete by beam tests

Numerical works

In addition to the experimental works, this study will also include the following numerical simulations using the structural analysis software ETABS15

- Numerical modification of nonlinear hinge
- Comparison of moment-curvature relationship between conventional concrete and ductile concrete
- Nonlinear static analysis assessing the performance of ductile concrete comparing with experimental data from static bending test
- Nonlinear dynamic analysis for the performance assessment under seismic load.

1.5 Organization of Thesis:

There are five chapters in this thesis.

Chapter 1 is an introduction of the thesis consisting of basic concept, context of the work (reason for choosing this topic), review of literature (i.e. previous works performed on this topic across the world), objectives (briefly outlines the possible works to be done in this study) and organization of the thesis.

Chapter 2 discusses about the chemical, physical properties of ECC which is specially used to this study and also practical application of such ECC.

Chapter 3 discusses the procedures of experiment and software application in different parts of this thesis.

Chapter 4 provides the results from numerical analysis as well as the results from experimental works, comparison between numerical data and experimental results and also the performance assessment of relevant study numerically and experimentally as well.

Chapter 5 provides the main conclusions of the thesis and recommendations for further study.

CHAPTER 2

DUCTILE CONCRETE

2.1 Introduction:

Micro fiber reinforced concrete is a revolutionary material that offers superior strength, durability, ductility, flexibility and aesthetic design. It is significantly superior to conventional concrete in terms of strength, ductility and toughness. It is blended with metallic PVA, polypropylene or some specific synthetic fibers, depending on strength and rheology requirements, exposure to corrosive agents, desired aesthetics and other factors. Available in a range of colors, it is extremely moldable and replicates form materials with great precision.

By utilizing the combination of superior properties, designers can create thinner sections and longer spans that are lighter, more graceful and innovative in geometry and form, while providing improved durability and impermeability against corrosion, abrasion and impact. The ductile behavior is a first for a concrete material, with the capacity to deform and support flexural and tensile loads, even after initial cracking.

Its superior strength allows for solutions with smaller elements, without the use of passive reinforcing steel and, in most applications, without prestressed or post-tensioned reinforcement. There is almost no carbonation or penetration of chlorides and sulphides. The material has improved freeze-thaw and abrasion resistance due to an optimized gradation. It is approximately 5% denser than conventional concrete. This 'denseness', along with small, similar-sized, non-connected pores throughout the cementitious matrix, attributes to its imperviousness and durability against adverse conditions and aggressive agents.

The material has almost no shrinkage or creep, making it suitable for prestressed applications. It is highly moldable due to the fine grain constituents, self-consolidating properties, and absence of reinforcing steel, thereby allowing designers to develop new, lighter complex shapes with enhanced surface aspects. Advantages may include: reduced global construction costs, formworks, labor and maintenance, which relates to improved site construction safety, speed of construction and extended usage life.

2.2 Mechanical Properties of ECC:

As mentioned earlier, the incorporation of fibers into cement-based composites mainly improves their toughness, bending, and tensile properties. This section discusses the effect of fibers on these properties.

Tension

Incorporation of fibers into cement-based composites can improve significantly the tensile behavior of the composites, including toughness, tensile strength, and failure mode. Usually, fiber-reinforced cement-based composites can be classified into two categories, according to their global tensile responses: strain softening or strain hardening. The strain-softening type of fiber-reinforced cement-based composites is usually reinforced with a low volume of short fibers. This kind of composite, containing about 1% fiber is typically used for bulk field applications involving massive volumes of concrete. Fig. 2.1 illustrates the tensile responses of such composites, with the incorporation of low-volume fiber fraction. For steel fiber-reinforced concrete specimens, the length, diameter, and volume fraction of the steel fiber are 48 mm, 0.5 mm, and 0.5%. For polypropylene fiber-reinforced concrete specimens, the length and volume fraction of the fibrillated polypropylene fiber are 50 mm and 0.5% (Zongjin Li 2011). It can be seen from the figure that although all the specimens display a softening behavior after the peak load is reached, the areas under the load-deformation curve are different and are larger for fiber-reinforced specimens than for plain concrete specimens. This implies that the fiber-reinforced specimens require more energy for fracture than do the plain concrete specimens. For a strain-softening type of failure, usually only one major crack is formed in the specimen. The fracture process of the material can be divided into four stages: the linear elastic stage (0~35% of peak load), the randomly distributed damage stage (35 to about 80% of the pre-peak load), the micro-crack localization stage (during the loading period between 80% of pre-peak load and 80% of post-peak load), and the major crack propagation stage (the period after 80% of post-peak load). A failure mode with multiple matrix cracking can be obtained when the cement-based composite is reinforced with either a high-volume fraction of short fibers or with aligned continuous fibers. Such high volume fiber composites have been used in thin sheets (e.g. curtain walls), slurry-filled cementitious composites, and concrete.

A typical strain-hardening curve for steel fiber-reinforced cementitious composites is shown in Fig. 2.1. There is a special point (marked B on the curve) called the *bend over point* (BOP) at which the matrix contribution to the tension capacity reaches a maximum. The stress-strain curve shown in the figure can be roughly divided into four stages. Stage 1 is from O to A in the figure, which is characterized by the elastic behavior of the composite until a few micro-cracks are initiated and are randomly dispersed at end of this stage. Stage 2 is from A to B. In this stage, randomly distributed micro-cracks start to localize and form the first major crack across the specimen's cross section at point B. The BOP corresponds to the end of Stage 2. The third stage is from B to C. In this stage, the incremental loading carried purely by the fibers at the position of the first crack is transferred back to the matrix through the bond and this process builds up the tensile stresses in the matrix again. The next matrix crack forms when the tensile stress exceeds the tensile strength of the matrix. The multiple cracking process continues until the minimum crack spacing is reached, at which the tensile

stress is transferred from the fibers back to the matrix cannot reach the tensile strength of the matrix. The process leads to an almost uniform distribution of fine matrix cracks. The fourth stage is from C to D. In this stage, no further matrix crack is expected and the additional load is sustained only by the fibers until failure of the fibers is reached. The phenomenon of strain hardening with multiple cracks is observed not only for continuous fiber-reinforced, cement-based composites, but also for short fiber-reinforced concrete.

Fig. 2.1: Qualitative Tensile stress-strain relationship of ECC (Zongjin Li 2011)

PVA Micro-Fiber Reinforced ECC has also ductile mechanical properties. Properties such as compressive strength, static modulus, flexural strength, moment-curvature, load-deflection behavior, first crack toughness, post-crack behavior, strain-softening behavior and ductility can be determined by laboratory tests. In Fig. 2.2(a) and 2.2(b) show results from investigations (Sameer Hamoush et al. 2010) on stress-strain property of PVA-ECC and moment-curvature relationship of beam section.

Fig. 2.2: (a) Stress vs. Strain property of PVA-ECC, (b) Section Moment vs. Curvature relation (Sameer Hamoush et al. 2010)

Bending

Cement-based Fiber-reinforced composites can achieve very good flexural strength and ductility. Fig. 2.3 shows that an extruded fiber-reinforced, cement-based plate exhibits a large deflection under four-point bending.

There is large deformation with a reasonably high stress, hence the area under the stress-strain curve is larger. That area can be used as an index to estimate the energy-absorbing capacity or toughness of the material. Increased toughness also means improved performance in resisting fatigue, impact, and impulse loading. Moreover, the improved toughness also leads to a better ductility.

Fig. 2.3: The large deflection of PVA-ECC beam

As mentioned earlier, fibers can be distinguished as microfibers and macro-fibers, according to their normal diameter and length. Fibers are also made from different materials that bring different properties into different fibers. A hybrid ECC uses more than two different fibers simultaneously Hybrid macro-fiber and microfiber-reinforced cementitious composite to optimize their advantages.

Fig. 2.4: Hybrid macro-fiber and microfiber-reinforced cementitious composite

By incorporating micro- and macro-fibers into a cement-based composite at same time, the microfibers can restrain the development of the micro-crack, while the macro-fibers can control the propagation of macro-crack. Hence the benefits of different size scales in restraining different size of crack can be fully utilized.

ECC exhibits many natural, physical qualities that allow it to be applied in place of standard fiber reinforced concrete as a more dependable, long-term replacement. These characteristics include its plastic damage, low permeability along with high tensile strength, flexibility and resistance to corrosion and spalling, or the fragmentation of the concrete under stress (Wu et al. 2006).

When stress is introduced to a sample of ECC, the major transfer of this stress is through the formation of micro-cracks in response to a tensile strain. The nature of these cracks is different from that of the cracks seen on other fiber reinforced concretes due to the fact that flat steady state micro-cracks are formed as opposed to localized Griffith crack propagation (Li & Li 2006). The former of the stress responses is ideal because when this type of micro-cracking occurs, it forms multiple, uniform cracks over a small area, whereas Griffith crack propagation forms large jagged cracks that are localized and harmful to the strength and permeability of the concrete. Under the conditions of steady state flat crack propagation, a process known as plasticity occurs where the material strength is higher after the first crack is formed and increases linearly to the final tensile strength factor. These cracks in ECC then follow simple formulae of crack potential and width that allows ECC to form smaller crack widths.

ECC has a large strain capacity of about five percent (500 times that of standard concrete), and an extremely low chance of the formation of localized fracture damage.

The formation of micro-cracks creates a unique resistance to the absorption of water and chloride ions which pose the greatest threat to the underlying structure of any reinforced concrete. Through experimentation and analysis, it was determined that ECC exhibits crack width well under the threshold of permeability for water and chloride ions under accelerated corrosion testing. When compared to that of normal concrete over a 14-week freeze thaw cycle, the traditional concrete was deteriorated at such a rapid rate, that it was removed from testing after five weeks. The ECC sample went on to complete the 14 weeks with no degradation of the surface or strength. Similarly, a 26-week test of ECC was conducted in a high temperature and alkaline environment, which, when complete, showed that the ECC dropped in tensile strain from 4.5% to 2.75%. While this seems to show a significant degradation in the concrete, similar traditional concretes are still 250 times weaker in comparison (Yang & Yu 2010).

Chen & Qiao (2010) demonstrated that a proper hybrid combination of steel fibers and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) microfibers enhances the resistance to both crack nucleation and crack growth.

On the other hand, combining different types and lengths of fibers can optimize the performance of FRC for specific benefits, such as improved processing, improved mechanical performance, improved durability, and reduced cost.

Yao et al. (2003) have constructed three hybrid composites using fiber combinations of polypropylene (PP) and carbon, carbon and steel and steel and PP fibers. Their test results showed that the fibers, when used in a hybrid form, could result in superior composite performance compared to their individual fiber-reinforced concretes.

Among the three types of hybrids, the carbon-steel combination gave concrete of the highest strength and flexural toughness, because of the similar modulus and the synergistic interaction between the two reinforcing fibers. Naaman et al. (2000) studied the performance of extruded thin sheet with hybrid fibers and found that the bending properties can be significantly improved.

A preliminary study on the hybrid FRC has demonstrated the good potential of such a composite, but how to get uniform dispersion of the different fibers remains a big issue in this type of composite. Both of the PP and PVA fibers' mechanical and physical properties are given Table 2.1 and 2.2.

Table 2.1: Mechanical and Physical Properties of Polypropylene structural micro-fibers

Configuration	Chopped fiber, resin-bundled chopped monofilament fiber
Lengths	6 mm or 12 mm
Tensile strength	70~100 ksi
Flexural Strength	1700~2100 ksi

Table 2.2: Mechanical and Physical Properties of PVA structural micro-fibers

Configuration	Chopped fiber, resin-bundled chopped monofilament fiber
Color	White or yellowish white
Specific gravity	1.3
Lengths and Diameter	¼ in. (6 mm), 1/3 in. (8 mm), ½ in. (12 mm), ¾ in. (18 mm) and Filament Diameter -8 Denier (38 Microns)
Tensile strengths	160~203 ksi (1100 ~ 1400 MPa)
Flexural Strength	3500 ~ 4200 ksi
Absorption	Minimal (< 1% by Weight)

2.3 Chemical Properties of Ductile ECC:

Concrete has fatal disadvantages; i.e. low tensile strength, a quasi-brittle nature, tendency to crack, low toughness, and low ductility. Since concrete was invented in the 19th century, many attempts have been made to overcome these disadvantages. The development of reinforced concrete using steel bars to carry out tension has advanced the application of concrete greatly. The invention of prestressed concrete has further improved the crack resistance of concrete. Later, incorporating high-strength, small-diameter fibers into concrete was developed to improve the toughness and ductility of concrete.

Two kinds of fibers are commonly used, continuous and short fiber. The use of short fibers seems to be preferable due to the simple and economical nature of the fabrication process. Experiments have verified that the response of the short fiber reinforced cement-based composites can be largely influenced by dispersion of the fiber. By adding the fibers to concrete, the toughness can be improved. However, due to increased cost and dispersion difficulties, short fibers cannot be added in large amounts. Thus, the improvement on tensile strength and toughness of concrete is limited. Another attempt at toughness improvement is to incorporate polymer into concrete.

While the durability of ECC is due to a low permeability and diffusion rate, along with a high tensile and compressive strength, the long lifespan is also due to a chemical process of self-healing that occurs inside the micro-cracks of the concrete. During the early stages of cracking (fewer than fifty micrometers), the concrete will engage automatically in a self-healing reaction that will mechanically fill in the micro-cracks. It takes place directly in the crack and under a multitude of environmental conditions ranging from freezing-thawing cycles to chloride submersion which allows the self-healing to be dependable in real life applications. This process of self-healing stems from the carbonation of the calcium in the cement matrix, but only occurs in the presence of specific acidity levels of the water and calcium ion concentration at the crack surface. As water moves more slowly through cracks of a smaller width, as opposed to quickly through larger cracks in regular Fiber Reinforced Concretes, pH levels will rise as carbonate precipitation occurs.

As the water, which contains carbon dioxide, penetrates the pores of hardened cement paste even deeper, it dissolves additional calcium ions from the calcium hydroxide. This then raises the pH value of the solution even more towards the ideal pH creating a more favorable environment for the self-healing process. The formation of CaCO_3 is the compound that will ultimately fill in the micro-cracks in which the reaction is occurring.

Experimentation has shown that a sample of ECC put under tensile strain and then subject to three wet dry cycles, will successfully fill a one hundred micrometer crack with calcium carbonate crystals. Additional testing in this experiment also showed that the introduction of fly ash to the ECC mixture would decrease average crack width to around ten micrometers, thus promoting a quicker and more filled self-healing sample (Li 2003).

The results of this experiment can be seen in Fig. 2.5.

The process of self-healing that ECC undergoes during this time has little effect on the tensile strength of the concrete: lowering the overall strength from 4.5% to 3%, a value well beyond that of standard fiber reinforced concrete. Along with this, the introduction of additives such as fly ash (an industrial waste resulting from coal-fired thermoelectric power generation) to ECC would allow it to be applied to situations where a more

consistent self-healing process would be observed. Certain other additives create different customized properties of ECC, including the ability to be sprayed as a much lighter material, higher tensile strength, or higher compressive strength. These various forms of ECC make it much more applicable to various commercial needs.

In China, under a national key research project on concrete, a study has been conducted to $nSi(OR)_4$, where R increases the toughness of concrete through incorporation of a new admixture. The new admixture is called concrete toughness enhancer. Its chemical composition is schematically shown in mineral matrix of concrete (cement or aggregates). With this new composite, a new generation of concrete can be produced. The concrete will have high tensile strength, and be very ductile of the modified concrete is significantly increased reference and the other incorporates the new admixture. The test results of two specimens are to verify the effect of the newly developed admixture, two types of concrete specimens which will be completely different from traditional concrete to reach the final goal. However, with our understanding of the nature of the concrete hydrates, especially the C-S-H, it is possible to develop a method and a material that can react with C-S-H and self-polymerization to

(a) Before self-healing

(b) After self-healing

Fig. 2.5: ECC (a) Before, (b) After self-healing

eliminate concrete's quasi-brittle nature and open an era for a new generation of concrete, i.e., the fourth generation of concrete.

Fig. 2.6: Schematic drawing of toughness enhancer structure
(Advanced Concrete Technology by Zongjin Li 2011)

An over view of chemical properties of PVA and PP fibers are shown in Table 2.3 and Table 2.4 respectively.

Table 2.3: Chemical Properties of PVA structural micro-fibers

Material	Polyvinyl alcohol
Chemical Formula	Idealized formula $[-CH_2CH(OH)-]_n$
Chemical Stability	Non-reactive
Corrosion Resistance	Excellent
Melting Point	435°F (225°C)
Safety	PVA is nontoxic
Degradability	Biologically Degradable

Table 2.4: Chemical Properties of PP structural micro-fibers

Chemical Formula	$(-CH_2-CH_2-CH_2-)_n$
Melting point	> 250°C
Chemical Stability	Non-reactive
Corrosion Resistance	Excellent

2.4 Sustainability and Environmental Impact of ECC:

Although ECC has a higher price than regular concrete, using even small amounts to repair beams, dams, bridges and other construction projects or to coat undamaged structures is an investment in the stability of the structure. This creates a more sustainable building material, reduces the price of repairs and the amount of materials used for repairs, and helps to lower the negative impact on the environment.

Cement is responsible for 3% of global greenhouse gas emissions. Every time 1 ton of cement is produced, 1 ton of CO₂ is released as well. When structures like roads are built with regular cement, they need to be repaired more frequently. This uses more cement which releases more greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. While a road is being repaired, the traffic in that area increases due to constructions and road closings. This congestion leads to increased fuel use and emissions. Using ECC can help to slightly decrease this environmental impact which improves the overall sustainability of the project.

The current accepted mixture of ECC includes a significant amount of cement so the adverse environmental effects associated with this material are still present in ECC. However, by substituting this with industrial waste such as sands, kiln dust, and fly ash, the environmental effects of the cement production would be reduced while also disposing of waste. 70% of ECC's composites may be replaced without reducing critical mechanical performance characteristics. Also the fly ash would not only lessen the negative environmental impacts of ECC manufacturing, it may also help to facilitate self-healing reactions better than in regular ECC mixtures.

Because sustainability is the ability of a process, method, or structure to endure over time and to support the endurance of society, the reduction of negative environmental impacts, the increase in the life-span of structures using ECC and the decrease in the amount of resources needed to repair these structures all show that ECC is a sustainable alternative to regular concrete. Using ECC as a commercial replacement for cement and FRC would lessen the environmental footprint of the cement industry through not only the reduction of emissions during manufacturing, but also through the reduction of repair materials necessary to keep structural conditions safe.

2.5 Practical Applications of ECC:

ECC may contribute to safer, more durable and sustainable concrete infra-structure that is cost-effective and constructed with conventional construction equipment. With two percent by volume of short fibers, ECC has been prepared in ready-mix plants and transported to construction sites using conventional ready-mix trucks. The mix can be placed without the need for vibration due to its self-consolidating characteristics. The moderately low fiber content has also made shotcreting ECC viable.

Furthermore, the most expensive component of the composite, fibers, is minimized resulting in ECC that is more acceptable to the highly cost sensitive construction industry.

Fig. 2.7: Completed ECC Link-Slab (Phase 1) on the Grove Street Bridge in Ypsilanti, Michigan

In Fall 2005, an ECC link-slab was constructed for demonstration by the Michigan Department of Transportation on a bridge in southeastern Michigan. This ECC link-slab replaced a conventional bridge deck expansion joint that had high maintenance costs associated with debris-induced joint jamming and cracking of adjacent slabs. The tensile ductility of ECC was exploited to accommodate imposed deformation from adjacent spans due to temperature variation, live load and drying shrinkage, while maintaining tight crack

widths for enhanced bridge deck durability. This first large-scale demonstration project (Fig. 2.7) in the US confirms the ability of ECC mixing and casting using commercial concrete ready-mix facilities and equipment. As indicated by the contractors, the self-consolidating nature of ECC makes it easy to apply in the field. The ECC link-slab project also served as a case study of infrastructure sustainability. ECC extends the service life of the link-slab by slowing the deterioration rate associated with steel reinforcement. Such ECC may also use in retrofit works.

R/ECC was adopted in the coupling beams of two high-rise R/C residential buildings (27-story Glorio Roppongi High Rise in central Tokyo and 41-storied Nabeaure Tower in Yokohama) under construction by Kajima Corporation in Japan. The precast ECC coupling beams connect the core walls on each floor, and reportedly provide high vibration damping and energy absorption during an earthquake. The new material technology enables structural engineers to achieve a more efficient building design and reduce construction cost.

Fig. 2.8 shows an illustration of the Nabeaure Tower in Yokohama completed in early 2007.

Fig. 2.8: (a) Nabeaure Tower in Yokohama, (b) Illustration of hybrid multi-tower showing the ECC coupling beam

CHAPTER 3

NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL WORKS

3.1 Introduction:

The numerical analysis performed in this study is done by ETABS 15, while some experimental works are done in the laboratory in an attempt to simulate the mechanical properties of ECC. This chapter briefly outlines the steps followed in the experimental works as well as the nonlinear pushover analyses and the dynamic response of ductile concrete under seismic and stepped loads.

3.2 Application of ETABS 15:

ETABS 15 is a powerful and reliable integrated software for the structural analysis and design of buildings with many features and functions. It has developed a completely integrated building analysis and design environment.

The integrated model can include moment resisting frames, braced frames, staggered truss systems, frames with reduced beam sections or side plates, rigid and flexible floors, sloped roofs etc. Design and analysis of steel and concrete frames, composite beams, composite columns, steel joints and masonry can be computed.

In addition to conventional analyses, nonlinear pushover analysis is possible after modifying hinge properties and dynamic analysis is possible through response spectra, as well as linear or nonlinear direct integration process.

3.2.1 Some Basic Parameters

Brief discussion on some basic parameters required for this analysis is provided below

Moment curvature relationships are very important to determine ductility (i.e. deformation capacity after the first yield) of a member/structure and the amount of possible redistribution of stresses. It is also very important for resistance against extreme loads like earthquake, impact and blast.

Moment vs. curvature ($M-\phi$) diagram for a typical cross-section is plotted with x -axis representing the curvature and the y -axis representing the moment, as shown in Fig. 3.1.

Fig. 3.1: Typical moment-curvature relationship

P-Delta Effect

P-Delta is secondary order loading effect in structural members. It is directly related to stiffness of structural elements. P-Delta effect is caused due to axial forces and geometric properties of the structural member. It affects the structural response performed by linear analysis, which neglects the effect of deformed shape in the analysis and design.

The P-Delta analysis in ETABS 2015 considers the effect of a single loaded state upon the structure. The following two methods are available in ETABS 15 for analyzing P-Delta effect

- *Iterative Based on Loads* - It is used as a specified combination of static load patterns. This may be the sum of a dead load pattern plus a fraction of a live load pattern. This approach requires an iterative solution to determine the P-Delta effect upon the structure.
- *Non-iterative Based on Mass* - This method is used as a story-by-story load upon the structure computed automatically from the mass at each level. This approach is approximate, but does not require an iterative solution.

Nonlinear Frame Hinges

Nonlinear Frame Hinges are used in nonlinear direct integration time history analysis. The following types of hinges can be used in ETABS 15:

- *Auto Hinge* - This type of hinge is formed as directed in the ASCE 41-13 codes. ASCE 41-13 code is valid only for some specified section, section length and material properties.

- *Manual Hinge* - Manual hinge can be used on the basis of Moment-Curvature relationship. Moment-Curvature found from material nonlinearity.

In this study, the sections, section length and material properties of the models did not match with the codes that are directed in the ASCE 41-13. So, manual hinges were used.

Damping

Damping can be defined as property of material and structure which influence dynamic response or vibration by internal friction and convert the mechanical energy into heat. It is very difficult to model damping accurately because it can be caused by various factors, such as

- Viscous effects
- External friction
- Internal friction
- Structural nonlinearities

There are two types of damping used for linear-elastic materials.

- *Viscous Damping* - Viscous damping force is proportional to velocity.

$$f_v = bv \dots\dots\dots(3.1)$$

Here,

f_v = Viscous damping force

b = Viscous damping co-efficient

v = Velocity

- *Structural Damping* - This type of damping is also called linear hysteretic damping. Here, structural damping force is proportional to displacement.

$$f_s = i Gku \dots\dots\dots(3.2)$$

Here,

f_s = Structural damping force

G = Structural damping co-efficient

k = Stiffness of structure

u = Displacement

i = Imaginary unit = $\sqrt{-1}$

Rayleigh damping is commonly used in nonlinear-dynamic analysis. To define Rayleigh damping, the damping matrix is assumed to be proportional to the mass and stiffness matrices. The equation is given as follows

$$[C] = a_0[M] + a_1[K] \dots\dots\dots(3.3)$$

Here, [C] = Damping matrix
[M] = Mass matrix
[K] = Stiffness matrix
a₀ = Mass-proportional damping coefficient
a₁ = Stiffness-proportional damping coefficient

For nth mode of such a system, the damping ratio can be written as follows

$$\zeta_n = \frac{a_0}{2} \frac{1}{\omega_n} + \frac{a_1}{2} \omega_n \dots\dots\dots(3.4)$$

If coefficients a₀ and a₁ are determined from the specified damping ratios ζ_i and ζ_j for the ith and jth modes, the above equation can express these modes in matrix form as follows

$$\frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1/\omega_i & \omega_i \\ 1/\omega_j & \omega_j \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} a_0 \\ a_1 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \zeta_i \\ \zeta_j \end{Bmatrix} \dots\dots\dots(3.5)$$

If it is assumed that both modes are form the same damping ratio ζ, coefficients a₀ and a₁ are determined by the equations given below:

$$a_0 = \zeta \frac{2\omega_i\omega_j}{\omega_i + \omega_j} \quad a_1 = \zeta \frac{2}{\omega_i + \omega_j} \dots\dots\dots(3.6)$$

(a) Mass-proportional and stiffness-proportional damping (b) Rayleigh damping

Fig. 3.2: Variation of modal damping ratios with natural frequency (Chopra 1994)

Time History Function

Acceleration was applied in the Global x-direction for time history analysis in this study. A time-history function was defined for applying acceleration. Different types of functions can be used easily. El Centro ground motion was used for numerical analyses in this study. El Centro ground motion,

which occurred at the Imperial Valley in southeastern Southern California on May 1940, was the first major earthquake recorded by a strong-motion seismograph. It had a moment magnitude of 6.9.

El Centro ground motion data is available in acceleration vs. time format. Original data has to be factorized by a scale factor for using. The original duration of El Centro data was 40.96 sec.

Fig. 3.3: Acceleration vs. Time (Original El Centro for 40.96 sec)

Out-put time step and the time step size

4096 data were used here for Fast Fourier Transform. The Fast Fourier Transform is defined as a technique which efficiently computes the coefficients of a discrete Fourier series. In engineering, the FFT is used most frequently to perform the operation of convolution. The engineering version of the FFT is computed for two sequences of time samples to be convoluted. The result of these computations is two scaled discrete Fourier series. The coefficients of these discrete Fourier series can be point wise multiplied to form the scaled discrete Fourier series of the desired output sequence.

If Direct Integration Method was used, the data would have been solved by Fourier transformation for any random number picked. But because of the out-put time steps, the nonlinear dynamic analysis may take a long time. Fast Fourier Transform is used to eliminate this problem and to do work easily. The accuracy of the solution is determined as the time step size. With the decreasing of the value of the out-put time step, the accuracy is increased.

In this study, the acceleration due to gravity 'g' is used as the scale factor. The scale factor is unit less.

Fig. 3.4: Out-put time step and the time step size form (ETABS 15)

3.2.2 Analysis by ETABS 15

This section describes in detail the steps in modeling structures by ETABS 15 for nonlinear pushover and seismic analysis.

Steps of Modeling

1. Go to the File menu > New model > Fill the grid dimensions (plan) and story dimension > Add structural objects (grid only). Fig. 3.5 shows the structural grid and story dimensions.

Fig. 3.5: Grid Dimensions and Story Dimension form (ETABS 15)

- Then Define > Material properties >Add new material >Material type (concrete)>Grade (3000psi)>Modify/Show material property design data as shown in Fig. 3.6.

Fig. 3.6: Material Properties form (ETABS 15)

- Stress strain property is modified from the experimental data, collected from ‘Deflection behavior of concrete beams reinforced with PVA micro-fibers’ (Sameer Hamoush et al. 2010).

Point Number	Strain	Stress (lb/in ²)	Point ID
1	-0.006	-1697.14	
2	-0.005	-2009.34	-E
3	-0.003461	-2546.54	
4	-0.001922	-3000	-B
5	-0.001345	-2818.79	
6	-0.000769	-2068.96	
7	-0.000192	-600	
8	0	0	A

Fig. 3.7: Modifying Stress-Strain property of material

- Define>Section properties>Frame section >Add new property (Rectangular)>Material (3000psi)>Size.

Fig. 3.8 shows cross-section properties of the structural member.

Fig. 3.8: Frame Section Property form (ETABS 15)

- Draw beam.
 - Select lower point of the column. Then Assign > Joint > Restraints > Fixed support > Apply.
- Fig. 3.9 shows the assigned joint restraints.

Fig. 3.9: Assign Support form (ETABS 15)

7. Select beam >Assign>Point load>Give the two point load values (Fig. 3.10).

Fig. 3.10: Represents the point load assigning

8. Define>Functions>Time history>Choose function type to add(from file)>add new function>Browse> Values are (Time and function values).

Fig. 3.11 shows the Time History function using modified El Centro data.

Fig. 3.11: Time History Function form (ETABS 15)

9. Assign>Joint loads>Force (only live load).

10. Define > Section properties > Frame nonlinear hinge > Add new property.

The form that is to be filled with required values is shown in Fig. 3.12.

Fig. 3.12: Frame Nonlinear Hinge form (ETABS 15)

The values of Moment and Curvature are defined from section designer. A graph for moment-curvature for a rectangular section is shown in Fig. 3.13, derived using ETABS 15 section designer option. The properties are defined from these respective values.

Fig. 3.13: Moment vs. Curvature from ETABS 15

11. Define > Mass source > check specified load pattern > add live & dead load (shown in Fig. 3.14).

The 'Define Mass Source' dialog box contains the following elements:

- Mass Source:**
 - Element Self Mass
 - Additional Mass
 - Specified Load Patterns
- Define Mass Multiplier for Loads:**

Load	Multiplier
Dead	1
Dead	1
Live	1

Buttons: Add, Modify, Delete
- Include Lateral Mass Only
- Lump Lateral Mass at Story Levels
- Buttons: OK, Cancel

Fig. 3.14: Mass Source form (ETABS 15)

12. Define > P-Delta options > Iteration-Based on loads > add live and dead load (shown in Fig. 3.15).

The 'Preset P-Delta Options' dialog box contains the following elements:

- Automation Method:**
 - None
 - Non-iterative - Based on Mass
 - Iterative - Based on Loads
- Iterative P-Delta Load Case:**

Load Pattern	Scale Factor
Dead	1
Dead	1
Live	1

Buttons: Add, Modify, Delete
- Relative Convergence Tolerance: 0.0001
- Buttons: OK, Cancel

Fig. 3.15: P-Delta Option form (ETABS 15)

13. Define > Load case > Add new case>Load case name (Gravity)>Load case type(Nonlinear static)>add>Load name (live) (as defined in Fig. 3.16).

Load Case Data

General

Load Case Name: Gravity

Load Case Type: Nonlinear Static

Exclude Objects in this Group: Not Applicable

Initial Conditions

Zero Initial Conditions - Start from Unstressed State

Continue from State at End of Nonlinear Case (Loads at End of Case ARE Included)

Nonlinear Case:

Loads Applied

Load Type	Load Name	Scale Factor
Load Pattern	Live	1

Other Parameters

Modal Load Case: Modal

Geometric Nonlinearity Option: None

Load Application: Full Load

Results Saved: Final State Only

Nonlinear Parameters: Default

Fig. 3.16: Load Case form (ETABS 15)

14. Define > Load case > Add new case > Time history

Now time history analysis should be performed with nonlinear direct integration method, as defined in Fig. 3.17.

Load Case Data

General

Load Case Name: LOAD Case

Load Case Type/Subtype: Time History

Nonlinear Direct Integrator

Exclude Objects in this Group: Not Applicable

Initial Conditions

Zero Initial Conditions - Start from Unstressed State

Continue from State at End of Nonlinear Case (Loads at End of Case ARE Included)

Nonlinear Case: Gravity

Loads Applied

Load Type	Load Name	Function	Scale Factor
Acceleration	U1	Ei centro	32.2

Other Parameters

Geometric Nonlinearity Option: P-Delta

Number of Output Time Steps: 4096

Output Time Step Size: 0.0037 sec

Proportional Damping: Mass: 1.563; Stiff: 0.0016

Time Integration: Newmark

Nonlinear Parameters: Default

Fig. 3.17: Load Case Time History form (ETABS 15)

Proportional damping >modify/show>specify damping by period.

Mass and stiffness Proportional Damping is input as shown in Fig. 3.18 [defining the natural periods and damping ratios in Eq. 3.6].

Fig. 3.18: Mass and Stiffness Proportional Damping form (ETABS 15)

15. Select > Properties > Frame section > Rectangular then Assign>Frame>Hinge [shown in Fig. 3.19].

Fig. 3.19: Hinge Assign form (ETABS 15)

16. Select > Properties>Frame section > Circular and Assign > Frame > Hinge overwrites>Relative Length of Frame Element at Hinge (0.02) [shown in Fig. 3.20].

Fig. 3.20: Hinge Overwrite form (ETABS 15)

17. Then run the analysis. After analyzing ETABS 15 can gives different types of result. Such as: Joint displacement, Joint Acceleration.

18. Display > Plot function >Joint Displacement for time history shown for different stories.

Fig. 3.21 shows the qualitative variation of a joint displacement with time, when the structure is subjected to ground motion.

Fig. 3.21: Displacement vs. Time from ETABS 15 analysis

3.3 Experimental Works:

The experimental part is basically associated with finding of material properties of microfiber reinforced concrete. The Fig. 3.22 shows the fiber used to make the concrete ductile.

Fig. 3.22: Polypropylene Fiber

Fig. 3.23 demonstrates the mixing of fiber with Sylhet sand before mixing in mixing machine.

Fig. 3.23: Polypropylene Fiber with Sylhet Sand

Oil treatment of wooden beam mold is shown after the figure 3.24, the oil is work for retaining the moisture.

Fig. 3.24: Oil treated wooden mold for beam (48" × 2" × 6")

Steel mold of briquette which is used to prepare samples of uniaxial tension test at figure 3.25

Fig. 3.25: Briquette Molds

Mixing of sand, cement and fibers into mixing rotary machine at the figure -3.26, a uniform gradual rotation is maintained.

Fig. 3.26: The auto rotary mix machine of concrete mixing

The rotary mixing machine of concrete is shown in Fig. 3.26, while Fig. 3.27 shows the condition of concrete after mixing.

Fig. 3.27: Concrete after mixing

Sampling for compressional test cylinder is at figure 3.28, the mold is made of steel.

Fig. 3.28: (4" × 8") Cylinder mold after concrete placing

Fig. 3.29: Specimen placed in Briquette mold

For controlling unexpected expansion the wire tie is used at mid-section of beam mold at fig.3.30

Fig. 3.30: Tie in mid position of beam mold to prevent expansion

Scattered positions of PP fibers after mixing is observed at fig.3.31

Fig. 3.31: Fibers alignments after mixing with concrete

All the samples are cured for 28 days as shown in Fig. 3.32 and 3.33.

Fig. 3.32: Submerged curing of bricked samples

Fig. 3.33: Wet curing of beam samples

Test preparations of cylinders is shown at 3.34-3.35

Fig. 3.34: Cylinder samples before test

Fig. 3.35: Deflection measuring gauge set up for cylinder

Failure mood of ordinary mortar and PP-ECC sample under UTM load is described at figure 3.36-3.37

Fig. 3.36: Plain concrete cylinder fully crushed due to compressive load

Fig. 3.37: Partially crushed view of ductile concrete (PP-ECC) under compression

Fiber bonding with the concrete material is observed at figure 3.38

Fig. 3.38: Failure surface of ductile concrete and the bonding between concrete and micro-fibers

Tension tools and setup with measuring gauge at figure 3.39

Fig. 3.39: Set up of Briquette Apparatus for Tension Test
Failure modes and surface of briquette samples after test shown at 3.40-3.42

Fig. 3.40: Failure of Briquette under tension

Fig. 3.41: Failure surface of Briquette under tension

Fig. 3.42: Failure modes and fiber bonding of ductile concrete

Beams experiments of pure bending with different samples is given fig. 3.43-3.44

Fig. 3.43: Sample beam for flexural load before and after

Fig. 3.44: Experimental set up of flexural strength test of ductile beam

Failure modes and surfaces of failures are shown at fig.3.45-3.48

Fig. 3.45: Full collapse of conventional concrete beam under flexural load

Fig. 3.46: Partially collapsed ductile concrete beam under flexural load

Fig. 3.47: Failure mode of ductile beam

Fig. 3.48: Non-uniformity of micro-fibers in concrete

The experimental mechanical property may be used in numerical analysis of ductile concrete for pushover and seismic analysis.

CHAPTER 4

NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

4.1 Introduction:

This chapter presents the results of laboratory experiments as well as numerical analyses including ETABS 15 push-over analysis and nonlinear dynamic analysis.

Experimental works (described in Chapter 3) determine the mechanical properties of ductile concrete. ETABS 15 analysis results can give absolute displacement of concrete structure and hinge formation in push-over.

This chapter describes ETABS 15 analysis results for simply supported beam, moment-curvature relationship of ductile concrete. It also describes the comparison between conventional and ductile ECC.

4.2 Results from Experimental Works:

The experimental works are associated with long span beam test, cylinder test and briquette test. While beam test gives load vs. deflection values under two point concentrated loads, compressive strength is found from cylinder test and the briquette test gives tensile strength and strain values of both conventional and ductile concrete.

4.2.1 Result from Compression Test

Cylinder of (4"×8") is used for the compression test of concrete. Comparative data show the performance of ductile concrete and conventional concrete. A table of compressive strength and strain of different cases is provided in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Material Properties of Conventional and Ductile Concrete under Compression

Sample No.	Conventional Concrete		Concrete with 0.4% PP fiber		Concrete with 0.8% PP fiber	
	f'_c (psi)	$\epsilon_{ult} (\times 10^{-3})$	f'_c (psi)	$\epsilon_{ult} (\times 10^{-3})$	f'_c (psi)	$\epsilon_{ult} (\times 10^{-3})$
Sample-1	6500	2.2	6900	4.0	4700	5.4
Sample-2	6500	2.6	6500	4.5	4700	6.0

4.2.2 Results from Tension Test:

Briquette specimen of (1"×1") is used to apply direct tension on concrete. The comparative data show the performance of ductile concrete and the conventional concrete. Table 4.2 shows the tensile strength and strain of different cases. Stains of PP-ECC are given for final cracks and (*) is for initial.

Table 4.2: Material Properties of Conventional and Ductile Concrete in Tension

Sample No.	Conventional Concrete		Concrete with 0.4% PP fiber		Concrete with 0.8% PP fiber	
	Tensile Strength (psi)	ϵ_{ult} (10^{-5})	Tensile Strength (psi)	ϵ_{ult} (10^{-2})	Tensile Strength (psi)	ϵ_{ult} (10^{-2})
Sample-1	330	10.0	290	(0.00025)* 6.3	290	(0.0004)* 7.0
Sample-2	340	9.8	270	(0.0002)* 5.8	290	(0.00037)* 6.8
Sample-3	290	9.0	220	(0.00015)* 3.8	230	(0.0003)* 5.4

4.2.3 Results from Beam Test

Long spanned beam (48"×2"×6") is used to apply two-point loading on concrete. Those comparative data show the performance of ductile concrete and the conventional concrete..A table of load respect deflection is shown in Table 4.3.

Graphical presentation of the load vs. deflection plots are covered from Fig. 4.1~4.6.

Table 4.3: Deflection from Pure Bending of Concrete Beam under Two-point Loading

Sample No.	Conventional Concrete		Concrete with 0.4% PP fiber		Concrete with 0.8% PP fiber	
	Load (lbs)	δ_{ult} (in)	Load (lbs)	δ_{ult} (in)	Load (lbs)	δ_{ult} (in)
Sample-1	1420	0.070	1150	0.090	1100	0.19
Sample-2	1400	0.061	1050	0.080	1050	0.15

Fig. 4.49: Load vs. Deflection curve of conventional concrete (Sample-1)

Fig. 4.50: Load vs. Deflection curve of conventional concrete (Sample-2)

Fig. 4.51: Load vs. Deflection curve of PP (0.4%) reinforced concrete (Sample-1)

Fig. 4.52: Load vs. Deflection curve of PP (0.4%) reinforced concrete (Sample-2)

Fig. 4.53: Load vs. Deflection curve of PP (0.8%) reinforced concrete (Sample-1)

Fig. 4.54: Load vs. Deflection curve of PP (0.8%) reinforced concrete (Sample-2)

4.3 Results from Numerical Works:

The numerical results consist of moment-curvature relationship, hinge formation in static non-linear (push-over) analysis of beam and response of a multi-storied building due to El Centro earthquake motion using Time History analysis with non-linear direct iteration by ETABS 15.

Results show the moment values with respect to curvatures, as well as and relative displacements of top stories.

4.3.1 Material Properties

Properties of normal concrete, PVA reinforced concrete and steel are shown. Compressive strength of both CC and ECC are assumed to be 3 ksi though the strain properties are different.

60-grade steel is used in all the numerical simulations for all sections. Mechanical properties of the materials are shown from Fig. 4.7 to 4.9.

Fig. 4.55: Stress-Strain Relationship of Conventional Concrete

Fig. 4.56: Stress-Strain Relationship of PVA-Reinforced Concrete (Sameer Hamoush et al., 2010)

Fig. 4.57: Stress-Strain Relationship of 60-grade Steel

4.3.2 Structural Properties

Structural elements of relevant beam, column, as well as multistoried buildings consist of their dimensions, support conditions and visual looks. The beam which is used for static non-linear numerical simulation has the dimension of (48"×2"×6").

The beam is analyzed with a support condition of simply supported beam.

Fig. 4.58: (a) Longitudinal view of concrete Beam, (b) Cross-Section of Beam

The concrete frame structure of six stories has all symmetric beam(12"×12"),column (15"×15") and (20"×20") and floor to floor height 10'. The ground storey is soft storey and the support condition is fixed.

Fig. 4.59: (a) Cross-Section of Beam ; (b),(c) Column

Plan and isometric view with dimension of 6-storied fame structure is shown in Fig. 4.12.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4.60: (a) Plan, (b) Isometric View of 6-storied of concrete building

4.3.3 Non-linear Static Analysis of Beam

The nonlinear static analysis data are associated with the stepped loading and the stages of hinge formation. Moment-Curvature relationship helps to predict the expected results. With the limitation of ETABS15 the 2''x6'' ordinary (3ksi) beam's Moment-Curvature is prepared by Forth-ran programming.

Moment-Curvature relationship is the key to this analysis and result as it is shown in Fig. 4.13.

Fig. 4.61: Moment-Curvature relation of Ordinary and PVA-ECC Beam of 2''x6'' section

Fig. 4.14 shows the failure and collapse prevention stages of 2''x 6'' beam in push-over analysis.

Fig. 4.62: (a) Deflection, (b) Collapse Prevention Stage, (c) Failure of Beam

Material and geometric nonlinearity are considered simultaneously. The elastic and plastic deformation results under two-point loading are shown in Fig. 4.15.

Fig. 4.63: Load vs. Mid Span Deflection of Conventional and Ductile Concrete Beams

4.3.4 Non-Linear Dynamic Analysis of Frame

Here the nonlinear dynamic analysis is based on Time History analysis with Direct Iteration method considering both geometric and material nonlinearity. Moment-Curvature relation is significant for the results comparing conventional and ductile concrete.

Moment-Curvature relationships for different cases are shown in Fig. 4.16~4.18.

Fig. 4.64: Moment-Curvature Relation of Columns (Steel Ratio = 0.0038)

Fig. 4.65: Moment-Curvature (15''x15'')Relation of Columns (Steel Ratio = 0.0074)

Fig. 4.18 shows that the moment vs. curvature relations of CC and ECC tend to converge with the increase of steel ratio of PVA-ECC.

Fig. 4.66: Moment (k-ft) vs. Curvature (rad/in) plot of same steel ratio of 2% (15''x 15'')

The ground motion which is used for Non-Linear Time History Analysis was obtained at the El Centro (or 1940 Imperial Valley) earthquake. The ground motion is shown in Fig. 4.19.

Fig. 4.67: El Centro Earthquake Ground Motion

Results for the numerical analysis by ETABS 15 of 6-storied ordinary concrete structure show the responses against time for seismic ground motion.

Fig. 4.20 shows the top storey relative displacement of the structure against time.

Fig. 4.68: Top storey deflection from TH-Analysis (15 seconds)

**Table 4.4: Survival Status of Ordinary CC against PVA-ECC by ETABS 15
(for El Centro ground motion)**

Cases	Ordinary CC Dimensions (columns)	PVA ECC Dimensions (columns)	Steel Ratio (ρ)	Survival Status
Case -i	15"×15"		0.01	Not survive
Case -ii	15"×15"		0.02	Survive
Case -iii		15"×15"	0.007	Survive
Case -iv	20"×20"		0.00	Not survive
Case-v	20"×20"		0.01	Survive
Case-vi	20"×20"		0.02	Survive
Case- vii		20"×20"	0.00	Survive

Plastic-Hinge formation for El Centro ground motion is shown in Fig. 4.20 which indicates the collapse prevention stage.

Fig. 4.69: Nonlinear Hinge formation in collapse prevention stage (a) low intensity (b) high intensity.

Fig. 4.22 and 4.23 show the variation of top storey deflection and 1st storey column moment of the 6-storied building with plain (unreinforced) 15" × 15" columns. The sudden failure of the plain concrete column and ductile behavior of the ECC is quite apparent.

Fig. 4.70: Top storey displacements of 6-storied building with symmetric frame and 15" × 15" column sections (plain PVA-ECC and plain concrete).

Fig. 4.71: First storey column moments of 6-storied building with symmetric frame and 15" × 15" column sections (plain PVA-ECC and plain concrete).

4.4 Cost Analysis:

Cost is of course the underlying criteria of choosing between conventional concrete and ECC. That's why despite the superiority of its mechanical properties, ECC will only be widely used if it is found to be cost effective compared to conventional concrete.

Table 4.5 summarizes the cost analysis of PVA-ECC with respect to the other classes of concrete used in this work, including CC, RC and Mortar.

The average price of PVA fiber in different manufacturing countries are, 0.24~0.48 cent /gram (China); 0.88 cent/gram (USA). The cost in China is taken for comparison in this study.

Table 4.5: Cost Analysis of PVA-ECC and other classes of Concrete and Mortar

Concrete Category	Volumetric Ratio	Cost/cft
CC	1:2:4	180
RC	1:2:4	330
Mortar (Ordinary)	1:2	212
PVA-ECC	1:2	224

With the variation of steel quality and grade, available prices of steel in Bangladesh about 30-60 Tk/kg and 4.5 - 5 kg steel is required per cft concrete if 2-2.5% steel is used.

Taking the minimum price of steel as 30 Tk/kg gives the probable cost per cubic feet of concrete to be 150 Tk. So, addition of steel cost with the CC cost gives 330 Tk.

CHAPTER 5

DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Introduction:

This chapter draws some conclusion on the works presented in the previous chapters, including results from nonlinear dynamic analysis of concrete structures by ETABS 15 and experimental works from compressive, tensile and bending tests to determine the material properties.

The chapter includes some discussion on the analyses, the laboratory experiments and comparison between results obtained.

Subsequently some suggestions on future work are also provided.

5.2 Discussions of Results:

- Fiber rawness, stage of adding fibers, rotations for uniform mixing highly influences the experimental result. So, exact mixing procedure is still under experimental supervision as it is very important in ECC constructions.
- Compressive strength of PP-ECC and Ordinary-Mortar are more than two times (6500 psi) compared to the strength of conventional RC or CC (about 3000 psi). In accordance the deflection at final crack PP-ECC is about 3-times (0.17 in) than Ordinary-Mortar (0.065 in).
- Experimental tension test gives strain in initial crack about 0.0003 and in final crack the strain is 0.06 which is 600 times more where the conventional one gives only 0.0001.
- Curvature of PVA-ECC (0.0025) is more than 100 times of normal concrete (0.00001) in Moment-Curvature relation prepared by ETABS15.
- The load capacity from Static Non-Linear (Push-Over) analysis of PVA-ECC is (1900 lbs) more than twice of Ordinary-Mortar (900 lbs) and the deformation is about 140 times (9 in) of ordinary one (0.065 in).
- Non-Linear Time History Analysis of multistoried building shows that for 15"×15" column size PVA-ECC can survive in El Centro earthquake with only 0.7% steel reinforced where RCC needs minimum 2% of steel. PVA-ECC does not require any reinforcement for 20"×20" column size, but RCC still needs minimum 1% of steel.
- Comparison of cost analysis shows that the ECC is economical as RC cost 330 Tk/cft where PVA-ECC cost 224 Tk/cft.

5.3 Recommendation for Further Studies:

- * Changing different parameters of experimental and numerical works may enhance the research scope of PVA-ECC.
- * Numerical modification and simulation of Moment-Curvature relationship of PVA-ECC can be forwarded.
- * Curvature vs. time plot may help for accurate nonlinear dynamic analysis.
- * The scopes of the parametric study may be boosted up with blast load, impact load etc.
- * Taking the advantages of economic view and eco-friendliness the PVA-ECC may be applied widely in mass constructions.
- * High-Rise buildings may be analyzed with PVA-ECC.
- * Comparative study of software application may be increased for numerical simulation (e.g. SAP2000, MIDAS, ABAQUS, ZeusNL etc.).

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